

“Determination of the Workability, Setting Time and the Compressive Strength of Concrete Made of Polystyrene Fibre”

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1.0 Abstract

This work presents the determination of structural characteristics of profile sheet-polystyrene fibre reinforced composite slab. It investigates the compressive strength, flexural strength and deflection of slab of profile sheet with concrete mixture of polystyrene beads, cement and sand with agro fibre reinforcement. The materials used include: ordinary limestone cement, fine aggregate, coarse aggregate, polystyrene beads, profile sheet, agro fibre, 10mm reinforcement bars, binding wire and water. Manual mixing operation was adopted, and all polystyrene concrete ingredients were batched by weight. Many number of cubes of size 150mm x 150mm x 150mm were produced from six different mix ratios of cement: sand: polystyrene beads, for compressive strength test. Also, a total of sixteen slabs of size 1200mm x 558mm x 125mm were cast for flexural strength of slab. Out of the sixteen (16) slabs cast; Twelve (12) were produced from profile sheet- polystyrene fibre reinforced composite with mix ratio 0.45:1:3:3 and six different fibre content in the mixture, two were produced from conventional composite having normal concrete ingredients (coarse aggregates, fine aggregates, cement and water) with 10mm rebar, profile sheet and mix ratio of 0.45:1:2:4. The remaining two slabs were made from plain polystyrene fibre reinforced slab with mix ratio of 0.45:1:3:3 and 0.31% Agro fibre content in the mixture, without profile sheet. The 28th day average compressive strength for the six mix ratios used were 4.81MPa, 5.3MPa, 6.2MPa, 6.4MPa, 4.33MPa, and 3.08MPa respectively. The **average static modulus of elasticity** for the six (6) mix ratios were 7.42GPa, 7.49GPa, 7.71GPa, 7.71GPa, 6.03GPa, and 3.66GPa respectively. The compressive strength of polystyrene concrete was below normal structural concrete value. Polystyrene concrete is a light-weight concrete in terms of density.

Keywords: Flexural strength, Agro fibre, Slab, profile sheet, polystyrene beads, compressive strength, static modulus of elasticity and deflection.

2.0 INTRODUCTION:

The slabs, beams, columns and foundations are part of the structural elements in a building. A planar structural element that has flat and two dimensions, best describes the slab element. The slab thickness is very small when compared to the other two dimensions. (Ibearugbulam, Ezeh, and Ettu, 2014). The primary role of a slab in a structure is to carry lateral loads, fixed and transient loads to beams and columns and it acts basically as a flexural member (Mosley, Bungey, and Hulse, 1999). It can be created from different construction materials like wood (timber), steel, and composite members like concrete, steel-composite etc. The EN 1994-1-1:2004 defines “composite slab as a slab in which profile steel sheets are used as permanent shuttering initially and subsequently combined structurally with the hardened concrete to act as tensile reinforcement in the finished floor. In this flooring/slab system, steel decking that are usually cold formed with different types of embossments are commonly used. This steel deck performs as a formwork during concrete casting in the service stage. For continuous composite slab, reinforcement steel is required at the support to resist the negative bending moment (Marimuthu, Seetharaman, Jayachandran, Chellappan, and Dutta, 2007).

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The design of concrete slab can be seen in BS 8110 parts 1, 2 and 3. The major challenge with concrete slab is self-weight. To solve the problem of self-weight for concrete slab, a lot of lightweight materials have been used as replacement to components of concrete. Industrial and agricultural wastes are among the lightweight materials that have been shown to be appropriate. which includes sawdust, palm kernel shell, fly ash, coconut shells, and pre-expanded polystyrene beads, among others which are produced from milling stations, industries and so on (Ganiron, 2014).

2.1 Objectives of Study: Over the years, composite slabs, commonly used in the building industry, has posed challenges of excessive self-weight. The studies centers on the determination of the workability, setting time and compressive strength of profile sheet-polystyrene fibre reinforced composite slabs for construction. The knowledge of this will help in improving the composite slabs, so as to know how to reduce the excessive weight of the element..

2.4 Scope of Study: The scope of this study is limited to determination of structural characteristics of profile sheet-polystyrene fibre reinforced composite slab. Compressive strength, static modulus of elasticity. The time of final setting of polystyrene concrete was determined.

3.0 MATERIALS: The materials used for this work were Portland limestone cement, Polystyrene beads, Profile sheet, fine aggregate (natural sand), coarse aggregate(crushed granite), Agro fibre, Water, 10mm reinforcement bars, binding wire.

i. Firstly the cement Dangote 3X Portland Limestone cement which conforms to NIS 44-1, part1 was obtained from a dealer in Owerri and used for all the work.

ii. To carry out this work, polystyrene bead was obtained from the Jik saw PLC at Industrial Cluster, Owerri North, Imo State, Nigeria. The diameter ranged from 3.1mm to 1.12mm.

iii. The aggregates used in this research work were coarse aggregate and fine aggregate. The coarse and fine aggregates used for this work were purchased from tipper stand at Owerri, Imo State Nigeria, it was sun-dried for seven days inside the laboratory before usage. The aggregates used were free from deleterious matters. The maximum diameter of natural sand used as fine aggregate was 5mm while that of coarse aggregate used was crushed granite of 19mm. The compacted bulk density of the coarse aggregate is 1615kg/m³ and the non-compacted bulk density is 1400kg/m³.

iv. Water from a well on the Federal University of Technology campus in Owerri, Imo State, was used for this study. The water meets BS EN 1008: (2002) standards and is potable. It is also suitable for curing and mixing concrete, as it satisfies drinking standards.

v. The profile sheet used for this research work were obtained from Owerri timber Market and the thickness is 1mm conforming to (2005, Eurocode 3). They were cut to 1200mm x 558mm x 75mm and used to produce slab of 1200mm x 558mm x 125mm.

vi. The agro fibre used in this project is from raffia palm tree and was bought from Afor Ogbe market in Ezinihitte Mbaise. The fibres were cleaned. The fibres were further dried in natural sunlight to remove moisture content and long uniform fibres were obtained.

vii. The reinforcement bars were purchased from a dealer in Owerri Timber market. The rebars were as specified in BS 4449:1997 and 10mm size reinforcement bars was used for the control slab.

viii. The binding wires were purchased from Owerri Timber market in Imo State and the Grade are as specified in BS 4449: 1997.

4.0 Methodology

4.1 Determination of Workability, and Setting Time of Polystyrene concrete

In this research work, slump test was performed on the mixes used to produce Polystyrene concrete fibre composite slab. Slump test gives good consistent results for a plastic mix. The test was conducted in accordance with the specification of BS EN 12350-2:2000. Second to that was the Penetration Resistance Test for Polystyrene

concrete While casting cubes to determine the compressive strength, flexural strengths, penetration resistance test was also conducted according to the specification of BS EN 12504-2:2012.

4.2 Determination of the Compressive Strength of Polystyrene concrete

The compressive strength of the polystyrene concrete used to create the fiber composite slab was ascertained by a compressive strength test. A manual mixing technique was employed to produce polystyrene concrete. For batching, the mix ratios were 1:6:0, 1:5:1, 1:4:2, 1:3:3, 1:2:4, and 1:0:6; these correspond to cement, sand, and polystyrene beads, in that order. The water-to-cement ratio was 0.45 for the entire mixture. The polystyrene concrete ingredients were batched by weight. Batching was done as per mix proportion see Table C1, page 122, Appendix. Cement and sand were mixed dry through, then properly mix these ingredients by adding water after that mix all by adding polystyrene beads, it makes uniform mixture. 150 x 150 x 150 mm molds were cleaned and lubricated to make it simple to remove the samples after they have set. Fresh polystyrene-concrete was poured into the molds in three layers, each of which was manually compacted after at least 25 blows. The surface was leveled once the compaction process was finished.

Six different mix ratios were utilized to create a total of 72 cubes. For each of the four curing ages—7, 14, 21, and 28—three cubes were taken from each mix. The 7th day's compressive strength was obtained using the first set of 18 cubes made from the mix ratios; the 14th day's compressive strength was obtained using the second set of 18 cubes; the 21st day's compressive strength was obtained using the third set of 18 cubes; and the 28th day's compressive strength was obtained using the fourth set of 18 cubes. After being submerged in water for a specified amount of time, the Polystyrene concrete cubes were tested using Okhard Machine Tool's WA-1000B digital display Universal Testing Machine (UTM). The machine conforms to the requirement of BS EN 12390-4 (2000) and has a testing range of 0-1000kN. The compression load at failure was recorded and used in Equation (4.1) to determine the compressive strength of the Polystyrene concrete.

$$\text{Compressive strength} = \frac{\text{compressive load of cube at failure (N)}}{\text{cross sectional area of mould (mm}^2\text{)}} \quad (4.1)$$

4.3 Density of Polystyrene concrete

The density of the cubes was obtained in accordance with BS 1881-114: 1983 The cubes for the compressive Strength Test were weighed in a digital weighing balance that has accuracy of 0.01g and recorded and the density of the samples were computed using Equation 4.2.

$$\text{Density} = \frac{\text{mass of sample (kg)}}{\text{volume of the sample (m}^3\text{)}} \quad (4.2)$$

4.4 Static Modulus of Elasticity of Polystyrene concrete

The static modulus of elasticity of the Polystyrene concrete were determined as a function of the compressive strength and density using Equation 4.3

$$E_s = (1 \cdot 7P^2 fC^{0.33}) \times 10^{-6} \quad (4.3)$$

Where ES =Static modulus of Elasticity

P= density

Fc= compressive strength.

5.0 RESULTS

5.1 Results

The results obtained for characteristic strength of polystyrene concrete and profile sheet-polystyrene fibre reinforced composite slab are presented here. The results of the test performed were tabulated as shown in Table 5.1, 5.2, 5.3, 5.4, 5.5, 5.6, 5.7 and 5.8

5.1.1 Workability

The results of the workability test were as presented in Table 5.1; from the results the level of slump can be ascertained.

Table 5.1: Workability Test Result for Polystyrene concrete

Mix Ratio (C:S:PS)	Slump Value (mm)	Type of Slump
1:6:0	110	True
1:5:1	100	True
1:4:2	100	True
1:3:3	95	True
1:2:4	115	True
1:0:6	120	Collapsed

5.1.2 Penetration Resistance for Polystyrene concrete

The results obtained from the final setting time of polystyrene concrete were as shown in Table 5.2 and Figure 5.1. The final setting time at 3.5MPa was 725 minutes.

Table 5.2: Penetration Resistance Test for Polystyrene concrete.

Elapsed Time (min)	Penetration Resistance (MPa)
50	0.0
100	0.0
200	0.7
300	0.8
400	1.0
500	1.7
600	3.1
700	3.3
800	4.1

Figure 5.1 Penetration Resistance Curve for Polystyrene concrete

5.1.3 Compressive Strength Test Results for Polystyrene concrete

The results of compressive strength at 7th day were as shown in Table 5.3. The average compressive strength for each mix ratio was as well computed for comparing purposes.

Table 5.3: 7th -day Compressive Strength Results for Polystyrene concrete

Mix ratio	Sample No.	Area of Sample (mm ²)	Weight of Sample (Kg)	Crushing load (KN)	Compressive Strength (N/mm ²)	Average Compressive Strength (N/mm ²)
1:6:0	A	22500	5.3	78	3.47	3.41
1:6:0	B	22500	5.29	74.1	3.29	
1:6:0	C	22500	5.45	78.1	3.47	
1:5:1	A	22500	5.43	76.57	3.40	3.74
1:5:1	B	22500	5.35	99.56	4.43	
1:5:1	C	22500	5.33	76.57	3.40	
1:4:2	A	22500	5.3	112.8	5.01	4.86
1:4:2	B	22500	5.28	103.7	4.61	
1:4:2	C	22500	5.3	111.8	4.97	
1:3:3	A	22500	5.3	117	5.2	5.0
1:3:3	B	22500	5.41	120.38	5.35	
1:3:3	C	22500	5.13	100.13	4.45	
1:2:4	A	22500	4.9	68.9	3.06	3.26
1:2:4	B	22500	4.34	75.56	3.36	
1:2:4	C	22500	4.8	75.45	3.35	
1:0:6	A	22500	4.2	52.05	2.31	2.28
1:0:6	B	22500	3.78	51.4	2.28	
1:0:6	C	22500	3.67	50.9	2.26	

Table 5.4: 14th - day Compressive Strength Results for Polystyrene concrete

Mix ratio	Sample No.	Area of Sample (mm ²)	Weight of Sample (Kg)	Crushing load (KN)	Compressive Strength (N/mm ²)	Average Compressive Strength (N/mm ²)
1:6:0	A	22500	5.46	86.32	3.84	4.04
1:6:0	B	22500	5.35	83.98	3.73	
1:6:0	C	22500	5.45	102.65	4.56	
1:5:1	A	22500	5.34	83.62	3.72	4.3
1:5:1	B	22500	5.48	110.04	4.89	
1:5:1	C	22500	5.2	96.53	4.29	
1:4:2	A	22500	5.36	123.45	5.49	5.6
1:4:2	B	22500	5.25	132.10	5.87	
1:4:2	C	22500	5.39	122.40	5.44	
1:3:3	A	22500	5.4	130.50	5.8	5.7
1:3:3	B	22500	5.36	127.13	5.65	
1:3:3	C	22500	5.13	127.13	5.65	
1:2:4	A	22500	4.87	77.09	3.43	3.60
1:2:4	B	22500	4.25	82.62	3.67	
1:2:4	C	22500	5.0	83.10	3.69	
1:0:6	A	22500	4.1	58.65	2.61	2.61
1:0:6	B	22500	4.0	57.96	2.58	
1:0:6	C	22500	3.81	59.5	2.64	

Table 5.5: 21st-day Compressive Strength Results for Polystyrene concrete.

Mix ratio	Sample No.	Area of Sample (mm ²)	Weight of Sample (Kg)	Crushing load in (KN)	Compressive Strength (N/mm ²)	Average Compressive Strength (N/mm ²)
1:6:0	A	22500	5.43	91.64	4.07	4.37
1:6:0	B	22500	5.37	92.87	4.13	
1:6:0	C	22500	5.43	110.25	4.9	
1:5:1	A	22500	5.54	123.10	5.47	5.49
1:5:1	B	22500	5.35	117.9	5.24	
1:5:1	C	22500	5.21	129.6	5.76	
1:4:2	A	22500	5.41	117	5.20	5.4
1:4:2	B	22500	5.36	120.6	5.36	
1:4:2	C	22500	5.0	126.95	5.64	
1:3:3	A	22500	5.36	138.38	6.15	6.2
1:3:3	B	22500	5.28	141.75	6.30	
1:3:3	C	22500	4.98	138.38	6.15	
1:2:4	A	22500	4.89	86.15	3.83	4.02
1:2:4	B	22500	4.36	92.67	4.12	
1:2:4	C	22500	5.1	92.8	4.12	
1:0:6	A	22500	4.13	65	2.89	2.95
1:0:6	B	22500	4.06	64	2.84	
1:0:6	C	22500	3.9	70	3.11	

Table 5.6: 28th-day Compressive Strength Results for Polystyrene concrete

Mix ratio	Sample No.	Area of Sample (mm ²)	Weight of Sample (Kg)	Crushing load in (KN)	Compressive Strength (N/mm ²)	Average Compressive Strength (N/mm ²)
1:6:0	A	22500	5.48	104	4.62	4.81
1:6:0	B	22500	5.37	98.8	4.39	
1:6:0	C	22500	5.47	122.2	5.43	
1:5:1	A	22500	5.44	100.75	4.48	5.3
1:5:1	B	22500	5.42	131.0	5.82	
1:5:1	C	22500	5.29	126	5.60	
1:4:2	A	22500	5.3	148.2	6.59	6.2
1:4:2	B	22500	5.26	136.5	6.07	
1:4:2	C	22500	5.41	133.65	5.94	
1:3:3	A	22500	5.27	144	6.4	6.4
1:3:3	B	22500	5.4	142.88	6.35	
1:3:3	C	22500	5.2	145.13	6.45	
1:2:4	A	22500	4.97	90.69	4.03	4.33
1:2:4	B	22500	4.36	100.75	4.48	
1:2:4	C	22500	5.0	100.75	4.48	
1:0:6	A	22500	4.13	69.4	3.08	3.08
1:0:6	B	22500	4.35	68.1	3.03	
1:0:6	C	22500	3.84	70.1	3.12	

5.1.4 Density Results for Polystyrene concrete

Before the samples were crushed, the 28-day weight of the compressive strength test was used to determine the density. The results are shown in Table 5.7.

Table 5.7: 28th-day Density Results for Polystyrene concrete

Mix ratio	Sample No	Volume of Sample in (m ³)	Weight of Sample in (Kg)	Density of the Polystyrene concrete in (Kg/m ³)
1:6:0	A	0.003375	5.48	1622.79
1:6:0	B	0.003375	5.37	1591.68
1:6:0	C	0.003375	5.47	1621.50
1:5:1	A	0.003375	5.44	1611.34
1:5:1	B	0.003375	5.42	1605.55
1:5:1	C	0.003375	5.29	1567.88
1:4:2	A	0.003375	5.3	1569.07
1:4:2	B	0.003375	5.26	1557.19
1:4:2	C	0.003375	5.41	1601.6
1:3:3	A	0.003375	5.27	1562.22
1:3:3	B	0.003375	5.4	1600
1:3:3	C	0.003375	5.2	1539.89
1:2:4	A	0.003375	4.97	1472.98
1:2:4	B	0.003375	4.36	1486.89
1:2:4	C	0.003375	5.0	1478.86
1:0:6	A	0.003375	4.13	1222.98
1:0:6	B	0.003375	4.35	1289.76
1:0:6	C	0.003375	3.84	1138.99

Average density of Polystyrene concrete is 1507.85Kg/m³

5.1.4 Static modulus of elasticity Results

The static modulus of elasticity results for each mix ratio were as shown in Table 5.8.

Table 5.8: Static modulus of elasticity Result for Polystyrene concrete

Mix ratio	Density of Sample in (kg/m ³)	Compressive Strength (N/mm ²)	Static modulus Of elasticity (GPa)	Average Static modulus of elasticity (GPa)
1:6:0	1622.79	4.62	7.42	7.42
1:6:0	1591.68	4.39	7.02	
1:6:0	1621.50	5.43	7.81	
1:5:1	1611.34	4.48	7.24	7.49
1:5:1	1605.55	5.82	7.84	
1:5:1	1567.88	5.60	7.38	
1:4:2	1569.07	6.59	7.80	7.71
1:4:2	1557.19	6.07	7.47	
1:4:2	1601.6	5.94	7.85	
1:3:3	1562.22	6.4	7.66	7.71
1:3:3	1600	6.35	8.01	
1:3:3	1539.89	6.45	7.46	
1:2:4	1472.98	4.03	5.84	6.03
1:2:4	1486.89	4.48	6.16	
1:2:4	1478.86	4.48	6.10	
1:0:6	1222.98	3.08	3.69	3.66
1:0:6	1289.76	3.03	4.08	
1:0:6	1138.99	3.12	3.21	

6.0 DISCUSSION.

The results presented above have been discussed in this section.

6.1 Workability and setting time of polystyrene concrete

The slump results for 1:6:0, 1:5:1, 1:4:2, 1:3:3, 1:2:4 and 1:0:6 for 0.45 water cement ratio are 110mm, 100mm, 100mm, 95mm, 115mm, and 120mm respectively. The mix ratio 1:6:0, 1:5:1, 1:4:2, 1:3:3, and 1:2:4 had true slump while the mix ratio 1:0:6 had a collapse slump.

More compaction resulted in segregation and polystyrene beads floated on the concrete surface. Much compaction is not advised in polystyrene concrete. Experimentally the workability increased with increase in polystyrene beads content, except 1:0:6 having only polystyrene.

6.2 Penetration Resistance Test

The penetration resistance of polystyrene concrete composite is 710 minutes while those of normal concrete ranges from 240 minutes to 480 minutes; this means that the presence of polystyrene beads increased the final setting time of concrete more than 38%.

6.3 Compressive Strength Test

The 7th day average compressive strength of polystyrene concrete ranged from 2.28MPa to 5.0MPa. The 14th day average compressive strength of polystyrene concrete ranged from 2.61MPa to 5.7MPa. The 21st day average compressive strength of polystyrene concrete ranged from 2.95MPa to 6.2MPa. The 28th day average compressive strength of polystyrene concrete ranged from 3.08MPa to 6.4MPa. This shows that increase in curing age increases compressive strength of polystyrene concrete up to 8.1%.

The values obtained for 28th day average compressive strength ranged from 3.08MPa to 6.4MPa with 1:0:6 having the minimum compressive strength and 1:3:3 having the maximum compressive strength. The values obtained are less than the minimum value of light weight concrete for 28th-day strength which should not be less than 17.5MPa for structural purposes.

Figure 6.2: Compressive strength of Polystyrene concrete and Curing Ages.

6.4 Relationship between Polystyrene concrete compressive strength of various mix ratios and curing ages.

The relationship between compressive strength mix ratios and curing ages graphs are presented as shown in Figure 4.3 to Figure 4.8, Equation 4.1 to Equation 4.6 describes the relationship between compressive strength, mix ratios and curing ages. From this Equation 4.1 to Equation 4.6, the compressive strength increases with increase in curing age.

For mix ratio of 1:6:0, the compressive strength relates with curing ages x as shown in Equations 6.1

$$F_c = 0.0647x + 3.025 \quad (6.1)$$

For mix ratio of 1:5:1, the compressive strength relates with curing ages x as shown in Equations 6.2

$$F_c = 0.056x + 3.345 \quad (6.2)$$

For mix ratio of 1:4:2, the compressive strength relates with curing ages x as shown in Equations 6.3

$$F_c = 0.0756x + 4.31 \tag{6.3}$$

For mix ratio of 1:3:3, the compressive strength relates with curing ages x as shown in Equations 6.4

$$F_c = 0.097x + 5.77 \tag{6.4}$$

For mix ratio of 1:2:4, the compressive strength relates with curing ages x as shown in Equations 6.5

$$F_c = 0.0519x + 2.895 \tag{6.5}$$

For mix ratio of 1:0:6, the compressive strength relates with curing ages x as shown in Equations .6

$$F_c = 0.0391x + 2.045 \tag{8.6}$$

Figure 6.3: Compressive strength of Polystyrene concrete for mix ratio of 1:6:0 and curing ages.

Figure 6.4: Compressive strength of Polystyrene concrete for mix ratio of 1:5:1 and curing ages.

Figure 6.5: Compressive strength of Polystyrene concrete for mix ratio of 1:4:2 and curing ages

Figure 6.6: Compressive strength of Polystyrene concrete for mix ratio of 1:3:3 and curing ages

Figure 6.7: Compressive strength of Polystyrene concrete for mix ratio of 1:2:4 and curing ages

Figure 6.8: Compressive strength of Polystyrene concrete for mix ratio of 1:0:6 and curing ages

6.5 Density Test

The average density of polystyrene concrete was 1507.85Kg/m^3 ; from literature, the density of light-weight concrete should not exceed 1840kg/m^3 . Therefore, polystyrene concrete composite is a lightweight concrete in terms of density.

Figure 6.9: 28th Day Density of Polystyrene concrete and mix ratios.

6.6 Static Modulus of Elasticity

The static modulus of elasticity of polystyrene concrete ranged from 3.66GPa to 7.71GPa; but the static modulus of elasticity of normal concrete ranged from 21.4Gpa to 46.4Gpa. This means the values obtained from polystyrene concrete were less than those of normal weight concrete.

Figure 6.10: Static Modulus of Elasticity of Polystyrene concrete and Mix ratios.

CONCLUSIONS.

The aim of the research is to determine the workability, setting Time and the compressive strength of the slab made of polystyrene concrete. Workability rises with increasing polystyrene bead content, and this concrete was considered medium workable by Shetty (2006). The concrete's typical final setting time ranged from 240 to 480 minutes. This means that the addition of polystyrene beads extended the setting time by more than 38%. The final setting time of 710 minutes was observed during the practical to establish the structural features.

The average compressive strength of polystyrene concrete composite ranged from 3.08MPa to 6.4MPa, which is far below the recommendations in ACI 213, (1987) which states that the minimum 28 days' strength value of light weight concrete should not be less than 17MPa for structural purposes. The value was below recommended value for normal structural concrete, but the value was within ordinary concrete value, which has its maximum as 10MPa. Based on the outcomes achieved so far, the following Recommendations were made. Firstly, studies should be carried out on how to improve the strength of profile Sheet-Polystyrene fibre reinforced composite slab using admixtures and secondly the relationship between deflection and flexural strength should be observed at different loading other than crushing load.

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